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Historical Background of Land Grants in Ancient India: An Analysis

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Abstract

The ruling elites of ancient India, it seems, were allured either to the gain of religious merit, evident from most of the epigraphic traditions that abundance of grants was either made to *Brāhamaṇas* or to the religious institutions; temples and monasteries or was impressed upon enhancing their social vigour. The authenticity of the land grant charter, being the royal documents of the state lends it more credibility as a primary source of doing history. The phenomenal rise in land grants, particularly in the later centuries of the first millennium might be because the idea of land grant as a pious gift was being popularized as sure bet against all sins. The piety of gift, especially land gift was a preserved tradition of the religious literature of India for a long time. There were numerous gifts enlisted in the classical literature of the early as well as early medieval India. But it seems as if the influence of the *Brāhmaṇas* increased than ever before and the concept of land as the noblest subject of the gift was propagated by them throughout this period.

Such gifts were usually registered with a royal sanction to uphold their validity as approved of by the ruler. It was an elaborate ritual that followed the sanction of grant to a *Brāhmaṇa* or to a religious institutions and utmost care was taken to make the process of registration foolproof with a view to guard the interest of the donees from the elements who could force eviction on the weaker donees and forge the documents to claim their legitimate rights; such incidents have been reported in the land grant charters where the sovereign ruler destroyed the forged document and reassigned the grant to actual beneficiary. This was for this reason that a metal plate was chosen over Stone and other perishable material to write down the contents of the land grant. The term *Tāmra-Śāsana and Rāja-Śāsana* occurs in our epigraphical source, obviously because the language of these grants mostly was Sanskrit.

That such a practice could be counterproductive could have far been understood beforehand as the nature of grants being made in this period was not that of a fixed tenure rather perpetual grants were made which were to stay there till the sun and moon shine; besides land grant charters made it binding upon all officials, people and the rulers succeeding them that no harm be caused to donees so should no atrocities be inflicted upon them. That was not all; there was a considerable shift in the elements of the grants. Earlier the grants were specified and boundaries were demarcated, perhaps to check the further encroachment by the beneficiary, but blame it upon the later rulers that they did not bother to introduce any system of checks and balances, hence facilitating the further expansion by the donees much beyond their prescribed boundaries.

Keywords Lang Grants, Land Charter, Royal Order, Brāhamaṇas, donees, Tāmra-Śāsana, Rāja-Śāsana etc.

Introduction

The word *Tāmra-Śāsana, Rāja-Śāsana* is a royal charter engraved on a copperplate, cloths and stone slabs. Ancient Indian Kings donated revenue-free

lands in favour of a person, deities or religious establishments, usually endowed with a deed engraved on durable *Tāmra -paṭṭa*, i.e. a copper-plate (the word has been frequently used in Early Medieval India after the Post-Gupta Empire). The copper-plates record various kinds of rent-free land donations to deities and *Brāhmaṇas* usually called *deyā-deyā* or *devā-dayā* and *brāhma-deyā* or *brāhmadayā* respectively. In certain copper-plates, the word *agrāhara* was more popular in the sense of a rent-free village in favour of *Brāhmaṇas* but it has been observed that this term was frequented more in southern India rather than north India.

Most probably the multiple Land grants in ancient Indian history played very significant role in defining the agrarian formation which certainly was an important adjunct of feudal economy. This feudal venture concluded in the central authority being deprived of their land rights and control and in creating a strong class of intermediaries which would hardly hesitate from exploiting the human and natural resources to the hilt. Landed aristocracy was neither bliss for the monarchical setup nor for the masses. Moreover, the king or the prior sovereign ruler has now distanced from its most efficient and productive class i.e. the peasants. Peasants, when transferred with the land to the donees, were the dumb subjects of oppression and atrocities. Hence it has repeatedly been argued that this vogue of land grants brought about the transformation of political power, reduced the peasantry to bondage and subjugation, and degraded the artisans to the lowest level of society. Though there were some disguised merits of the advent of feudal introduction the spoils of such a venture were the prerogative of top notch gentry once again. The plight of the peasantry was such as never before. Besides losing their primary rights in land and over the cultivation, which they held without an objection as in the confidence of sovereign ruler, they subsequently lost the right to labour as well.

The term land can be defined as rural or agricultural area, distinct from the urban area, primary contributor in the process of production indispensable for human sustenance. The land could further be classified as uncultivable, cultivated, fellow, barren, low, high, hilly, marshy, etc. D.C. Sircar observes that the whole early medieval northern Indian land could be divided into the following categories: state land and the land in the occupation of the tenants who paid the king's dues according to agreed rates, over which the effectiveness of the state control varied under different circumstances. Each of these categories could be subdivided into different types.

In further classification, all land could broadly be divided into five categories; land attached to the king personally, the fields attached to the members of the royal family, officials and subordinates, etc.; land cultivated by the state farms, land cultivated by *adhikas* who were temporary tenants accruing half of the share of the produce for their labour, and the uncultivated and waste land of various types.

The king or the monarch was not only the administrative head of the country in ancient times, but he was assumed to be blessed with some divinity. He was bestowed with the honour of the saviour acting as the supreme protector of people after the God. As evident from the classical sources of ancient India, Kautilya in *Arthaśāstra* for example places the prosperity of the public as the prime objective of the king in the very opening of his treatise. It was on this score that the king was considered the owner of all kinds of land, and the tenants first enjoyed the right of building and occupying houses and cultivating the fields on payment of certain dues to him. But the king's rights in respect of the ownership of land were often relegated in various degree, to the vassals, fiefs holders and privileged tenants who may be regarded as landlords under the primary ownership of land, viz., the king. However, there was a difference of views between two groups of early Indian scholars as regards the king's ownership of land. One of these two scholars, represented by Jaimini and Sabara and others, hold that the state was not the owner of all land, but was only entitled to collect revenue or impose taxes on the holders of the land. There was a certain area which is under the core administration of the state but not the whole country from which it collected revenue on account of providing protection. It is therefore argued that the whole earth cannot be donated by the king to the donees under the pretext of his virtual claims of ownership. Even Megasthenes considers King as the sole owner of the land in early India and he elaborates that no private person was permitted to own land during the Mauryan times. But taking Megasthenes statements at its face value would be a biggest folly

for the reasons quite obvious; one that the actual work of the author has never been found intact in its entirety and it is only in the writing of Arrian and Strabo that the fragments of *Indica* are compiled, second that Megasthenes was in Mauryan court in the capacity of an Ambassador hence the true picture of the Mauryan administration could not be presented to him for security reasons. Even if Megasthenes views are taken to be true it becomes quite apparent that the understanding of the ownership and land control that we have today might not have developed in those times hence went unnoticed. The state system had not aged even three centuries. Notion of ownership as we have conceived today might not have been the characteristic feature of those times.

Early Indian literary sources or traditions contain quite a number of references about land grants made by the kings or dignitaries other than kings to *Brāhamaṇas*, monks, temples, monasteries and secular persons, for both religious as well as secular purposes. Contrary to the general belief, we come across references of land donation in later Vedic literary tradition; where land grants were made only to the ecclesiastical persons and their establishments. But it can be argued that the nature of grants has varied throughout its journey all the way from early to early medieval India

Objective of study The main objectives of the study of this research deals with the multiple layers on the basis of historical development as socio-economic rights transferred to new donees along with full administrative powers had been enjoyed by the donees. How this theory of extension of the Royal control was soon to be proven counterproductive. Let alone the enhancement of the royal dignity, such a system created a class of rivals which posed a threat of internal collision over petty matters in the absence of strong central authority. Donees who before had little significance in society and almost no say in the administrative and financial matters could now exercise their amateur expertise to regulate their reward

Review of Literature

The serious research on the agrarian economy of early medieval northern India began in the second half of the 20th century C.E. when debates started over the nature of the land economy, types of rights over land and the tenancy in early and early medieval India. This invited the various scholars to remark with their understanding the characteristics of land control and its impact on the society and economy of early medieval India in particular. However, the credit goes to D.C. Sircar, together with N.N. Kher and Om Prakash who brought the land system/land grant into the study of Indian history for the first time. R.S. Sharma, D.D. Kosambi, V.K. Thakur, D.N. Jha, B. Chattopadhyay and G.C. Chauhan are some other historians who have discussed the nature and type of land grants in their respective writings.

The work of these scholars is a valuable contribution to the study of the land economy in early medieval India but the scope of the theme has however been restricted to the nature and type of land grant and archaeological sources have not been fully utilized.

U.N. Ghoshal, (1929, 1940), *The Agrarian System in Ancient India Contribution to the History of Hindu Revenue System*, made undoubtedly the most considerable contribution to this interesting theme. Ghoshal's information is extensive and based on a voracious study and precise delineation. D.D. Kosambi, (1965), *An Introduction to the Study of Indian History*, attempts to distinguish two processes in the development of feudalism in ancient Indian history that is 'feudalism from above' and 'feudalism from below.' When the kings began to transfer their administrative rights to their subordinates chiefs who thus came into direct relation with peasantry this process he calls, 'feudalism from above'. L. Gopal, (1965, 1980), *Economic Life of North India C.E. 700-1200 and Aspects of the History of Agriculture in Ancient India*, Author discusses the various approaches and techniques of agriculture in ancient and early medieval Indian land economy. He suggests the private ownership of agricultural land in early medieval northern India but at the same time, he states that the king had a proprietary right over donated lands.

D.C. Sircar, (1966, 1969), *Land System and Feudalism in Ancient India; Landlordism in Ancient and Medieval India as Revealed by Epigraphical Records*, shows that his works are certainly a proof of the author's learning and extensive reading. But Sircar's works on the land grant are based on the wrong assumption

that the pattern of land grant till recent time continued to be the same. He is not inclined to accept the presence of Feudalism in Ancient India. He states that the landlordism has been confused with feudalism.

B.N.S. Yadav, (1973), *Society and Culture in Northern India in the Twelfth Century C.E.*, his work is a valuable contribution to the study of the history of early medieval northern India. Author's total rejection of the loss of the king or the state control over donated land may be especially notable in early India when land grant was less in number and religious in nature. But one cannot entirely rule out the loss of the state control over donated land from 8th century C.E. onwards. Om Prakash (1988), *Early Indian Land Grants and state Economy*, is a single work on land grants which covers our period of research. Om Prakash is the view that land grants were not uniformly a drain on state resources; instead, they enriched the state in various ways. R.S. Sharma's (2005, 1987, 1985, 1983), work *Early Medieval Indian Society: A Study in Feudalization, Urban Decay in India: C.300 to C.1000, Indian Feudalism, and Perspectives in Social and Economic History of Early India*, deal with the land economy and feudalism in ancient India. The author bases his whole thesis of Indian feudalism and theory of urban rot on land grants system as reflected in literary and epigraphical sources of ancient India.

Early Medieval Indian Society: A Study in Feudalization, the author goes beyond this traditional view of feudalism. The author attempts to expose the dominant groups which used land grants, control of common services, caste and religion as a tool to gain control over the means of production. *Perspectives in Social and Economic History of Early India*, this work begins with a survey of the sources of the social and economic history of early India and reviews the writings from the late nineteenth to the mid-twentieth centuries on social history. B. Chattopadhyay (1994, 1990), *The Making of Early Medieval India; Aspects of Rural Settlements and Rural Society in Early Medieval India*, is primarily a collection of essays that together seek to explore the processes and nature of change in Indian society over a period of about approximately between the seventh and the thirteenth centuries.

Aspects of Rural Settlements and Rural Society in Early Medieval India, Chattopadhyaya in this work highlights various aspects of the early medieval period has always shown disagreement with these approaches. He focuses on the changing social and spatial profiles of the early medieval rural settlements belonging to three different regions.

G.C. Chauhan,(2003, 2004,2013, 2015), *Economic History of Early Medieval Northern India*, G.C. Chauhan attempts to present the picture of the agricultural development and economic change which early medieval northern India has experienced. His work presents a comprehensive and systematic study of the economic institutions such as agrarian formation, feudal economy and the nature of peasantry in early medieval northern India. He is the view that the widespread land donation generated a new class of landed aristocracy and feudal lords and ultimately state suffered not only the loss of revenue but also the state control over donated land.This book comes handy while researching into the economic aspects of the given period particularly as gleaned from the various literary and epigraphical sources.

Origin and Growth of Feudalism in Early India, he traces out the modest origin and growth of feudalism in early India from the Mauryas to 650 C.E. He further states that the Indian feudalism cannot be a replica of Western feudalism and cannot be taken as such. The European feudalism originated, grew and got maturity in an entirely distinct socio-economic and political milieu and its geographical factors shaped its social structure and India's had its own. On the land grants pattern in early India, Chauhan is of the opinion that land grants played very important and crucial role in the socio-economic and political formation of early India. The state-controlled economy of pre-feudal period got transformed into a feudal economy through the issuing of land grants which generated a landed aristocracy; it is supposed to have brought about the fragmentation of political power, reduced the peasantry to bondage and subjection, degraded the artisans and ultimately paved the way for the conquests and subjugating of India by many foreign elements. He clarifies his take on how the system of land grant led to the rise of feudatories and subsequently to the weakening of the state and ultimately leading to fragmentation.

Agrarian Economy of Ancient India, G.C. Chauhan discusses about the economic dimensions of land grants of early medieval northern India seventh century onwards, he further states that the earlier concept of enjoying land-grants, and certain kinds of land grants had been donated to different people religious as well as secular people as a remuneration for their services to the state or king. No doubt, the fashion of making land grants in Indian history was as old as *Brāhmaṇs* and Buddhist literature, but it has been used in different perspectives in different periods. *Early Indian Feudal Society and Its Culture*, he highlights social and economic aspects of land grants but did not touch upon the political aspects of land grants which played very vital and decisive role in state formation in ancient India. Chauhan states about the feudal social formation in early India through the feudalisation in education institute, subjugation of artisans.

Thus after a long and detailed evaluation of literary and epigraphical sources and works of various scholars and historians, it can be surmised that the system of land grants, which gained much currency in early medieval India evolved in its form and nature from the beginning of early Indian history. Though no hard and fast rule as for the kind of land donation was laid, neither in early nor in later period, the land was randomly donated, sometimes as a settled village, and at other times a part of the village, and yet another times a village including the periphery such as small marketplace or huts. A significant number of land grants was made of the barren lands and land on the outlying regions specifically on the principle of *bhūmicchidranyāya* with a view to encourage the agrarian expansion via bringing vast regions under the plough and also relieve the crowding settled places perhaps any further. This, as attested by the Kautilya goes true for Mauryan period when more land was needed to be brought under cultivation to satiate the ever-increasing demand of surplus, perhaps the most important ingredient of a militarily expanding state. Also in those times, comparative less area was brought under cultivation which provided a scope for agrarian expansion. Again by bringing large terrains under direct or indirect control meant to enhance the political glory of the kings. It was comparatively easy to govern and administer the settled area where the heat royal authority could be felt. In later stages the basis of land grants, the agrarian expansion became a bleak prospect of economic regulation. The system of land grant gave rise to a new class of landed aristocracy or intermediaries emerged which slowly pushed away from the land control and eventually the finances from the central authority. It not only alienated land but the masses from the sovereign rulers who in the least were concerned about some of the basic rights of peasants. But new overlords were more profit-obsessed and not so considerate about the good governance. Rather their control was a transfer of power which was not guided by the principles of monarchy. This was the biggest gap between the traditional monarchy and the new overlord who emerged as a result of feudal phenomenon catalyzed by the lands grants to *Brāhmaṇs* and *Brāhmaṇical* institutions.

The above review of the literature does not provide us with the clear picture of the socio-economic life of early medieval northern India in its totality with the special references to land grant charters which reflected the social and economic changes and development which early medieval northern India witnessed.

Main Text

Origin and Development of the Land Grants:

The reference to land-grants are found in the literary sources of later Vedic times as well, few to be listed are *Śatapathā Brāhmaṇs*, *Āitrareya Brāhmaṇs* and *Chāndogya Upaniṣad*. It is evident from the *Dharmasūtras* that land was granted to *Brāhmaṇs*, monks and their religious establishment as pious gifts for destroying all sins discussed before that the idea of giving gifts to *Brāhmaṇs* for gaining some spiritual and religious merits besides getting freedom from all sins was being popularised in which *Brāhmaṇism* was a major tactic player. With religion becoming ideologically dominating, transformation from *vedic* religion to the later one occurred where

The similar land grants are reproduced in the later law book and the *Mahābhārata*. Many land grants made to the *Brāhmaṇs* and secular persons find their record in the *Mahābhārata* and the *Rāmāyana* as well records a grant of one hundred villages. The term '*parihāra*' is mentioned in the *Mahābhārata* for the village from where the soldiers were recruited in the armed forces. This indicates that some land might have been granted to the soldiers as well in addition to their

salaries. It might as well suggest that the trend of giving the secular grants in lieu of salaries was not even a new idea in an early medieval period of Indian history. *Yajñavalkya* suggests that the city council had the right of bestowing grants, and the land was donated along with labour working on half of the produce. It seems that peasant was bonded to the donee but the extent of such bonding was limited and not just another adjective of exploitation and oppression. It was only in the later periods that subjection and subjugation of the peasants in an illegitimate manner went unbridled in the absence of some regulating authority that could keep a tight check upon such practices. Also, it would convince us that right from the beginning, peasantry, though the most indispensable for our material existence failed to impress the ruling elites and another gentry of their relative significance and self-dignity. Even in the noblest cases of the land transfer where even peasants were not subjected to oppression, peasants were hardly involved in the decision making which would henceforth decide upon their lives.

The Buddhist literary traditions point towards abundant of references regarding land donation. *Jātakastories*, *Baudhayāna*, *Mahāvastu* and *Dhammapada* inform us that land grants were donated by royal kings or private persons to the religious as well as secular purposes. Land donation adopted as a means for religious piety was not the sole prerogative of kings. Private or secular individuals were too allowed to make such grants out of their land possessions but it was binding upon them to take the prior permission for such donations to *Brāhmaṇs*, monks and any other person or religious establishment which might have been donated on some payment in shape of a compensation for the loss of revenue to the state. This reference though contrary to the statement that all land was owned by the king, suggests that private ownership existed in ancient India though its extent and the form could have been unknown or how could ever be the donor of the land had there been no land rights secured by him. Also, it shows that given the matters associated with land control, the state was the supreme authority hence mandating the prior permission or sanction from it. We, therefore, come up with a resolution to such a problem where terms, ownership and land right create confusion as for deriving their meaning in the strict sense of terms. We suggest that, for time immemorial, the ultimate ownership has been claimed by ruling authority be it a republic government, monarchic setup or a democratic government but what we confuse with private ownership is just the right that an individual or an institution could exercise in the confidence of the sovereign ruler. Therefore in early India the King boasted to be the owner of the whole earth under the pretext of providing the occupants of these territories the protection against all odds and also of bringing them under a uniform organization or administration and in lieu of all this, peasants or other inhabitants, whatever vocation they are engaged in, must provide king with tax for such an organization to run smoothly. It seems as if the system of state emerged from the inspiration of symbiotic relationship where the mutual benefit was a basic tenet; it was only towards later period that such principle faded away and the stronger party assumed the exploitation of the weaker as its legitimate right.

However, *Arthaśāstra* records the *brāhmadeyā* land grants to those *Brāhmaṇas* who performed sacrifices effectively for the state and were donated land in lieu of cash salary; it further maintains that the *brāhmadeyā* lands were granted with some immunities and privileges and were exempted from the taxes and fines. *Arthaśāstra* records another type of land called *Ātithya* donated to certain state officials such as *gōpas*, *Sthānika*, *Adhyakṣa*, the veterinary doctors and the physicians in lieu of the cash salary without the right of sale or mortgage. When *Arthaśāstra* makes clear mention of the limited rights of the donee upon the land, it becomes apparent that rights though not listed as elaborately as in early medieval period but were limited by the state for some definite reasons. The want of more territories might have inspired donation of land for the dual benefits of religious merit, payment of dues and as well to bring the vast barren expanse under extensive cultivation, needed for surplus production and guard against all natural and unnatural calamities. Kautilya was a great visionary and he rather comprehended the significance of land rights to be retained by the king even if some privileges out of it were alienated as a part of the grant. Secondly, the tradition of granting land, as the obsession of rulers might not have set in.

Kautilya also suggests the units of economic and political administration; *sthāniya* consisted of 800 villages, *droṇmukha* of 400 villages, *karvatikā* of 200 villages and a small unit was *saṃgrāhana* of 10 villages. It is suggestive of the point that these land grants were given to officials by the state in lieu of cash salary even

though their rights might have been limited as implied before. The above references conclusively prove that the provision of granting land to the state officers as substitution of cash salary was present during the Mauryan age. The system of paying state officials through land grants was further strengthened during the times of Manu. Manu suggested that the *adhipati* of 10, 20, 100 and 1000 villages be granted lands in lieu of cash salary for their services which they provided to the king.

Since there is no inscriptional evidence to supplement such an argument in pre-Mauryan India we suppose that land grants might have been recorded on a piece of cotton cloth and wooden plate or any other perishable item that could not stand the tortures of times and vanished away. The *Vaiṣṇava Dharmasūtra* states that the king or state granted land to the donees and the records were written upon a piece of cotton cloth or a copperplate. We find hosts of inscriptions from Mauryan period onwards recorded on copper plates or stone pillars. Such inscriptions offer us information about personages and events of India's past on which other sources are conspicuously silent. The contemporary events were recorded in most of the inscriptions and so they are to be relied on.

A number of land grants were mentioned in epigraphic records of early India. A mango garden was donated by the second queen of Aṣoka. *The Nanaghat Cave inscription of Queen Naganika* (first century B.C.E.) records the grant of a village at the *Aśvamedha* Sacrifice; the donee seems to be a *Brāhmaṇ*. This was a religious grant and no immunity has been recorded.

The Karle Buddhist Cave inscription of Gautamputra Sri Satakarni (99 to 123 C.E.), records grant of a village named Karajaka to monks for the support of the *Mahāsaṃghikas* with certain immunities. This inscription shows that the royal officers were not supposed to enter the donated village and the donee was to enjoy (all kinds of) immunities. It can hence be inferred that King abstained from enjoying any administrative right over the donated village. It could be marked as the beginning since the rulers had started to give away lands with other important rights and resources, giving them an almost independent control. Although unlimited power or rights as suggested by the inscription could be brought into question, yet it is quite certain that privileges provided in the grant were much more than the preceding grants. Similar kinds of grants were recorded in the *Karle Buddhist Cave of Sri Pulumavi* (130 C.E.). *The Nasik Cave inscription of Sri Pulumavi* (149 C.E.), which mentions a grant named Sudasana to the monks with certain immunities such as, not to be entered (by the royal officers), not to be touched (any of them), not to be dug for salt, not to be interfered by district police also comprises yet another kind of grant which came with the assurances of certain exemptions. Eventually, the king had even given up his right over mines which were considered to be not only a Royal privilege but the insignia of state authority as well. We also learn from *Arthaśāstra* that state alone was entitled to the income from mines.

Most of the Saka and Satavahana rulers donated land to Buddhist *Samghas* for the welfare of the Buddhist creed and fraternity as a result of which the Buddhism prospered and its followers were in most privileged position under their rules. The motive behind these grants may have been to earn religious merit as well for the donees. The epigraphic fragment records donations or investments of the field by the lay worshippers which generally include the opulent merchants, the householders, and the monks. Such donations were made for the support of the monks, repairs of the porch and the Pavada, expenses of lamps to Buddha and providing clothes to ascetics, etc. The fields were also given by the lay worshippers for planting *Jambu*, *palmyra*, *sāl*, mango, and *karanga* trees. Sometimes the fields were granted by the individuals to the guilds to invest their income for plantation of trees.

The Nasik Buddhist Cave inscription of Uravadata tells us that he purchased a field from the *Brāhmaṇ* Asuitbhuti for 4000 *karṣapaṇas* and later on granted it to the Buddhist *Samgha*. The royal grants were generally issued to the donees for increasing fortune, wealth, power, the length of life and victory in war, etc. Such grants were made with proper ceremonies i.e., libations of water, from the lands of the donors so that the donees and the transaction were to last as long as moon and stars exist. It seems that a uniform protocol of donation of land had developed in early medieval India which had some religious and spiritual

significance. The grantees could enjoy the grant perpetually seems apparent from the verses of declaration such as; this land is to be enjoyed by the donee for as long as the sun and the moon endure. The grants ended with an imprecating to these appropriated the donation or transgressed or causing any trouble to the donees.

Generally, the rulers issued royal grants and sent commands to their district officers for further necessary formalities. We notice that many grants were also made by the feudatory rulers in the pre-Gupta period. Usavadata, the viceroy, and son-in-law of Nahapana issued three land charters. *Mahārathi* Somadeva, a feudatory of King Sri Pulumavi made a royal donation of a village, and King Visnukadda Chuta Satakarni II, probably a feudatory of the Pallava king Siva-Skandavarman also granted land.

It has been mentioned in the *Poona plates of Prabhavati Gupta* (fourth century C.E.) that the village named Dariguna was granted to the *Brāhamaṇs* and others free of all hindrances and carried certain immunities, such as village was not to be entered by soldiers and policemen, it was exempted from the obligation to provide grass hides as seats and charcoal to the touring royal officers, it was exempted for purchasing fermenting liquors and digging (salt), exemption were made for rights upon mines and *Khādīra* trees, it was also exempted from the obligation to supply flowers and milk. The rights to collect taxes were given to the donee with the privilege of exemptions mentioned above.

The plates of Pravarasena II (fifth century C.E.), refers to the grant of the village Kothuraka to the celibate *Brāhamaṇs* by Pravarasena II with certain immunities, such as donee was not liable to pay any sort of dues, taxes or tribute to the state, his estate was not supposed to be entered by the state officials, soldiers, and policemen. The state was not entitled to demand it of the customary cows and bulls; donee was not obliged to pay royalties on flowers and milking. Donee was also exempted from the obligation to provide grass, hides as seats and charcoal as it was exempted from the royalties on the purchase and fermenting of liquors and digging together with the right of hidden treasures and deposits together with all taxes. The nature of Grant seems to be perpetual which means that it was declared, the donee could retain all rights mentioned above without a question or interference as long as sun and moon endured. An appeal was also made to the future kings and officials that they were to protect the rights of the donees. Officials were not allowed to interfere with either the administration or with other economic procedures of the granted territories failing to comply which could attract penalty as prescribed in the punitive procedures of the period. Also a religious fear was struck into their brain by declaring that such a culprit would be responsible for a thousand sins.

A grant of the village named Chammak consisting of eight thousand *navaratanas* to thousand *Brāhamaṇs* of various *gōtra* was mentioned in *the Chammak plates of Pravarasena II*. *Siwani plate of Pravarasena II* records the donation of a village namely Brahmapuraka to the *Brāhamaṇs* with the right to levy a tax equal to one-fifth. *The Rddhapur plates of Prabhavatigupta*, also records the grant of a field to *Brāhamaṇs* together with house and four huts of farmers. That sometimes land was donated along with the inhabitants is clear from this charter, it is also clear that peasant seem to be attached to the soil, but not in the same sense as it was in Europe. The serfdom of Europe differed from the Indian system of peasant subjection and subjugation in many ways where focus was on producing more with a less labour. *The Indore plates of Pravarasena II* refers to the grant of half of the village to the *Brāhamaṇs* by the merchant after purchasing from the state. It indicates that private person was entitled to donate land to the donee too but with the prior permission of the authorities.

The Nalanda Copper-plate inscription of Samudragupta refers to the grant of the village to *Brāhamaṇs* named Jayabhattsivamin and it had been written at the order of Gopasarmin, Aksoptaladhikrta; the *Gaya Copperplate inscription of Samudragupta* (328-29 C.E.) mentions a grant of a village Revatika to the *Brāhamaṇs*. This grant seems to be a non-sectarian which was given in certain condition to the donees. They were ordered that cultivators and artisans should not be allowed to enter into the village (*agrāhara*) otherwise it would be taken back from him. Sometimes state officer used to grant land to the *Brāhamaṇs* and secular person after purchasing land from the state. *The Damodarpur Copper-*

plate inscription of Visnugupta (542-43 C.E.), mentions that *Amytādeva a kulapūtra* from Ayodhya applied to the town court of Kotivarsa district for the purchase of some khilā or waste land for the establishment of *bāli, cāru, saṭṭra*, etc., and for the repair and for the supply of the materials for daily worship of God and five *kulyavāpas*. *Vindhyasakti II* refers to the grant of the village Akasapadda to the certain *Brāhamaṇs* of the *Atharvaveda*. Though it becomes clear that the transfer of peasants and entire occupants was effected when a settled village was donated to a religious or secular donee yet what boggles our mind is the question as to who were settled in the khila land or barren land as mentioned in the above land grant, as a need to mobilise a huge manpower to bring such lands under cultivation was but obvious.

There are multiple examples of the land donation where land is first being purchased then being handed over to the donees. This is suggestive of the fact that the prevalence of the tradition of donation of land to the *Brāhamaṇs* for the religious merit or for some other reasons was so deep rooted that the consequences of such donations were completely overlooked by the donor.

The issuing of grants and the procedure to inform one and all reflect the two aspects of purpose of such a practice, one that it be informed to one and all that hereafter the land rights had been transferred to a new beneficiary and that all should acquaint with the new overlord, secondly it does not reflect the discrimination of any kind towards the masses by the state where all were considered equal and the witness of even an individual belonging to lower social order held some impact. Even if this practice was a mere formality, some elements of rare equality before the state could be gleaned from it.

The Banskhera Copper-plate inscription of Harṣa, records the donation of the village named Markatasagara to two *Brāhamaṇs* of Bharadvaja *gōtra*. Donees were exempted from paying all taxes and were provided with all immunities by the state, another copperplate of Harṣa. The *Madhuban Copper-plate inscription* (631 C.E.), refers to the grant of the village called Somakundaka to Samavedi Bratta Vatsavarmin of Samarni *gōtra* and *Rgvedi gōtra*. It was taken away from the Vamarathya who had been enjoying it on the strength of forged documents. The village was donated to the donees with full right of inheritance by Harṣa. The grant of Harṣa states that a village was granted in favour of two *Brāhamaṇas* as an *agrāhara* rent free holding usually in the possession of *Brāhamaṇas* in accordance with the custom governing its acceptance by *Brāhamaṇas* so that the customary privileges going with such holding remained understood. And villagers were asked to be obedient to the donees and to pay them the usual dues *pratyaya* including *tulya, meyā, bhāga, bhōga, kāra, hiraṇya*, etc.

Examination of copper-plates of early India and early medieval India is a mammoth task which not only demands peculiar set of skills but also some historical acumen. In conclusion, it can be said that a vast area of land was donated either to *Brāhamaṇas* or monk or to religious establishments and secular persons right from the early centuries of B.C. projecting towards the times of Harṣa. The gradual accumulation of lands by *Brāhamaṇas*, monks, religious establishments and other secular persons helped the growth of a class of intermediaries which became the vassals or *sāmanta* at later stages. This was feudalism in the setting right from the beginning of the land grant tradition as viewed by G.C. Chauhan has contested the view of R.S.Sharma particularly who regards the land grant as the basis of feudalism by saying that if land grants were to be taken as criteria for feudalism; its origin could be pushed much back.

Though no hard and fast rule as for the kind of land donation was laid, neither in early nor in later period, the land was randomly donated, sometimes as a settled village, and at other times a part of the village, and yet another times a village including the periphery such as small marketplace or huts. A significant number of land grants was made of the barren lands and land on the outlying regions specifically on the principle of *bhūmicchidranyāya* with a view to encourage the agrarian expansion via bringing vast regions under the plough and also relieve the crowding settled places perhaps any further. This, as attested by the Kautilya goes true for Mauryan period when more land was needed to be brought under cultivation to satiate the ever-increasing demand of surplus, perhaps the most important ingredient of a militarily expanding state. Also in those times, comparative less area was brought under cultivation which provided a scope for

agrarian expansion. Again by bringing large terrains under direct or indirect control meant to enhance the political glory of the kings. It was comparatively easy to govern and administer the settled area where the heat royal authority could be felt. In later stages the basis of land grants, the agrarian expansion became a bleak prospect of economic regulation. The system of land grant gave rise to a new class of landed aristocracy or intermediaries emerged which slowly pushed away from the land control and eventually the finances from the central authority. It not only alienated land but the masses from the sovereign rulers who in the least were concerned about some of the basic rights of peasants. But new overlords were more profit-obsessed and not so considerate about the good governance. Rather their control was a transfer of power which was not guided by the principles of monarchy. This was the biggest gap between the traditional monarchy and the new overlord who emerged as a result of feudal phenomenon catalyzed by the lands grants to *Brāhamaṇs* and *Brāhamaṇical* institutions.

We notice from the literary and epigraphical sources that land was granted to the gods, *Brāhamaṇs*, monks under the maxims of *bhūmicchidranyāya*, which meant that the donated land was to be enjoyed as a free holding. There are many aspects of the term *bhūmicchidranyāya* which could imply to a particular law governing the system of land grants in early medieval India or more specifically as an institution to develop or harness more natural resources from the barren land to provide an impetus to state economic growth. There seems some flexibility in the system of land grants when this prerogative was imbibed by the lesser officials like governors or vassals who had to seek permission of the overlord before making any kind of grant and also if they wanted to create a free holding in his fief or estate in favour of a god or religious persons, he applied to the kings and apparently paid the price of the land.

It can be deduced that the villagers were required not only to render general obedience to the donee but they were also supposed to pay him the usual dues from the villages in terms of the contribution in kind, the tax in cash and so forth. The lands were donated to the donees with all types of immunities. The land was declared to be enjoyable by the donee and by his posterities perpetually with all types of immunities. The householders headed by the *Brāhamaṇs* and artisans or else are ordered to pay the donee. Now they used to pay customary dues called *bhōga bhāga hiraṇya* and other revenues to the donee, in the place of the state, which resulted in the drastic loss of revenue to the state exchequer.

However, it is evident from the study of land grant charters that the *Brāhamaṇs* were very influential and occupied a high status in society because of their accessibility to learning and on account of their right to officiating at sacrifices and rituals performed by the rules and wealthy class. They received grants sometimes whole village famous by the term *agrāhara*. This type of grant, specifically made to *Brāhamaṇs* meant a lot of privileges and free exemptions. The land grants not only increased their economic status but also gave them administrative authority over such *agrāhara*. The *agrāharas* had been donated to the donees on a permanent basis and revenue of the concerned land was utilized by the donee. Sometimes rulers also transferred to the donees his right over the water resources, salt mines, hidden treasury and right to decide criminal and civil cases and impose fine on thieves.

Therefore, from the literary and archaeological sources of early India, it can be gleaned that the beneficiaries and some private persons were allowed to exercise their fiscal, judicial and administrative right over donated lands. This was the predominant feature of later centuries of the first millennium, particularly the *Pālā* period that started to alienate most of the rights of the state.

The literary references to the land grant found between Buddhist times to Harṣa periods demonstrate that feudal immunities or exemptions given to the donees of the subsequent period were virtually very less. The donees were very much under the direct control and authority of their overlord. A strict rule was maintained to extract their obedience to land. But the thing was, however, seems to be little modified in the Satavahana inscriptions. A distinct landed intermediary class emerged owing to the consistent grant of land, this class had sufficient say over their tenants and on their part, they made every possible effort to differentiate themselves from large peasantry class under their jurisdiction. The state had to suffer the loss of control over the land. The land still belonged to the state had

got the right to evict the donees, if it was not satisfied with the concerned donees.

The Gupta and post-Gupta periods witnessed a marked change in the land holding pattern. The state was no more to enjoy its right over the donated land. The *sāmantas* and donees were its real owner and as consequences, the peasantry too owed their allegiance to the donees (*sāmantas*) or vassals. As a result of these changes in the land system, the state lost not only revenue but also the land. The subjects and army were more vigorously tied to the feudal lords since it was they who in effect were in charge of their salary and well-being.

Conclusion

The purpose of the grant of land might be many; the king might have sincerely desired to bring uncultivable land under cultivation as discussed before, secondly by granting the land in the far-flung areas where the royal authority was little felt by the people could show the presence of central authority. In this way the king could exert its influence in such areas where the people were oblivious of central authority prior to the grant was affected. But this theory of extension of the Royal control was soon to be proven counterproductive. Let alone the enhancement of the royal dignity, such a system created a class of rivals which posed a threat of internal collision over petty matters in the absence of strong central authority. Donees who before had little significance in society and almost no say in the administrative and financial matters could now exercise their amateur expertise to regulate their reward. To further worsen the situation, the control of communal land and the joint land was also given away to the donees resultantly the communal land ceased to exist. The idea of the welfare state was frittered away and masses were considered not more than a landless labour that had the obligation to work on the mercy of beneficiaries or die of hunger.

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